

Transient Current Responses of Organic Electrochemical Transistors: Evaluating Ion Diffusion, Chemical Capacitance, and Series Elements

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For the successful implementation of organic electrochemical transistors in neuromorphic computing, bioelectronics, and real-time sensing applications it is essential to understand the factors that influence device switching times. This work describes a physical-electrochemical model of the transient response to a step of the gate voltage. The model incorporates 1) ion diffusion inside the channel that governs the electronic conductivity, 2) horizontal electron transport, and 3) the external elements (capacitance, ionic resistance) of the ion dynamics in the electrolyte. This work finds a general expression of two different time constants that determine the vertical insertion process in terms of the transport/polarization parameters, in addition to the electronic transit time. The work highlights the central role of the chemical capacitance in determining the modulation of the lateral conductivity. The different types of response of the drain current are classified, and the significance for synaptic operation in neuromorphic circuits is discussed. The model is confirmed by detailed simulations that enable to visualize the different ions distributions and dynamics.

insertion and extraction of ions from an electrolyte and subsequent ion diffusion in the channel, while the compensating electronic carriers are established from drain and source contacts.^[10–13]

OECT are excellent for translating chemical signals, such as ions or neurotransmitters, into electrical signals, as well as for accurately controlling stable conductance states to efficiently emulate computational tasks performed by biological synapses such as short-term depression (STD), short term potentiation (STP), and long-term potentiation (LTP).^[14] However, fully capitalizing on OECTs requires a deeper comprehension of their fundamental transistor operation mechanisms, particularly regarding transistor switching behaviors, which play a pivotal role in the training phase of the neural networks. Controlling the device relaxation times is essential to increase the nonvolatility of neuromorphic transistor elements,

by slowing down the ionic response, or inducing electrochemical reactions.

The switching properties have been investigated recently^[15–25] and different conclusions have been obtained, regarding effects of the size of the cation, asymmetry of cation injection and extraction. The main approach to analyze the switching transient is the Bernards-Malliaras (BM) model,^[13,16] that captures the coupling of cation insertion and the compensating electronic charge, by combining the electronic transient time across the channel, τ_e , and the time τ_i , associated to series connection of the ionic resistance of the electrolyte and the gate with a capacitance.^[26] However, it is generally understood that the diffusion step of cations inside the channel is a dominant factor of the switching dynamics, and this was not included in BM.^[27,28] The diffusion charging has been investigated for many years, starting with the conducting polymer films,^[29–31] and also in the organic transistors.^[32,33] Recently, asymmetric switching times have been observed upon charging and discharging, and they have been interpreted as lateral diffusion currents along the channel.^[25,34,35]

In our previous work, we developed a general transmission line model of OECT considering drift electronic transport and ionic injection and diffusion across the organic film, driven by the gate voltage.^[27] The derived analytical model describes the dependence of drain current on gate bias in a time-transient situation,

1. Introduction

Organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) are presently under investigation for a variety of applications, including bioelectronics, logic circuit components, and neuromorphic devices.^[1–7] In the OECT the channel is formed by a mixed ionic-electronic conductor.^[8,9] The variable electronic conductivity is obtained by

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Figure 1. a) Scheme of the measurement of transient response of the OEECT. b) Scheme of distribution of currents. c,d) The blue arrows indicate the stationary electronic current $I_d^{st} = I_s^{st}$. The green arrows are the transient charging electronic currents. In a transient situation, the difference of green currents at Drain and Source electrodes, $I_d - I_s$, equals the total ion current entering the channel film (red arrows). The voltage distribution for a small V_{ds} is indicated for two situations: (c) $\theta = -1$, $V_{ds} < 0$, and (d) $\theta = +1$, $V_{ds} > 0$.

according to the measurement outlined in **Figure 1a**. However, experimental patterns are more complex, due to the influence of capacitive and resistive elements in the electrolyte and its interfaces to the gate and channel. The impedance expression of the general model, recently derived,^[36] including series impedances in the electrolyte, provides additional insight to the transient behavior in more complex situations. Here we apply the theory of transients to show the types of decays that can be expected, their physical interpretation, and their evolution with the ratios of internal parameters of the system.

There are many general treatments of the dynamics of OEECT using complete simulation programs, that describe well different aspect of the dynamical behavior.^[1,37–39] However, since the device has so many potential parameters and phenomena, the simulations are not so easy to interpret in comparison to experiment. The focus of the present work is different. Here we aim to obtain the key dynamical components that govern the transient response using some simplifying assumptions. This will enable us to use equivalent circuits model in parallel to the time transient physical equations. Then we can obtain profound insight as how different effects interact and produce observed responses in current transients. We will provide a detailed analysis of the simplifying assumptions and their limitations and discuss how different experimental techniques can be used in concert to clarify physical interpretations. These methods can improve the application of the OEECT in neuromorphic circuits^[1] and in amplifying electrode-based biosensors.^[40] We also compare the results of the simplified model with full physical simulation of OEECT.

2. Transients in the Ion Diffusion Model

2.1. General Transport-Conservation Equations

We summarize the previous results for the transients measured in the configuration of **Figure 1a**. The main elements of the model are outlined in **Figure 1b**.^[27,36] The dominant physical processes consist of (a) ionic diffusion from the electrolyte to fill the channel at the equilibrium concentration imposed by the gate

voltage (injected current I_v), combined with (b) drift electronic transport across the channel, of charge injected from source and drain contacts (horizontal current I_h). The general equations of the system have been described elsewhere for both accumulation and depletion mode OEECT.^[27,36] L is channel length, d is channel thickness and w the width, μ_p is the hole mobility, and D_{ion} is the ion diffusion coefficient inside the organic film. The framework we use here solves the central problem of vertical ion dynamics combined with horizontal electronic carrier transport. We remark that additional phenomena can occur in the OEECTs such as limiting horizontal transport of ions, or vertical transport of holes.^[10,11,34,35]

The following conventions are used for the voltages and currents. The variable voltages are denoted u_g (the gate voltage), u_d (the drain voltage), etc.; the voltages of the stationary point are denoted V_g, V_{ds}, \dots , and finally, the small perturbation voltages are named v_g, v_d, \dots . The gate current is I_g , drain current is I_d , and the stationary currents are I_k^{st} . The I_d is positive in the x direction in **Figure 1b**. Small perturbation currents are denoted i_k . The vertical small perturbation gate current is i_g and the drain current is i_d .

Let us consider an accumulation mode OEECT with injected anions of volume density $a(x, y, z)$. The case of depletion can be treated similarly, as described before.^[27] We define A , the average concentration of anions per unit horizontal distance in the channel, as

$$A = w \int_0^d a \, dy \quad (1)$$

This is the concentration in the slice of **Figure 1**. The vertical injection current depends on the diffusion flux J_v at the boundary as

$$I_v = -q w J_v (y = 0) \quad (2)$$

The I_v is a current per unit length, entering the slice of **Figure 1b**, so that the total gate current is $I_g = L I_v$. The charge

conservation in the small volume of the slice implies that in the horizontal direction

$$\frac{dI_h}{dx} = I_v \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, the injected ions satisfy the diffusion equation and the conservation equation:

$$J_v = -D_{ion} \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial J_v}{\partial y} \quad (5)$$

with the diffusion coefficient D_{ion} and the boundary condition $J_v (y = d) = 0$.

The application of Kirchhoff rules combined with diffusion^[30] produces the classical equations of a two coupled transmission line models that have been applied to OECT in many works.^[19,38,41–43]

Under certain simplifying conditions of charge homogeneity in the vertical direction, that are discussed in Sec. 2.5, the vertical diffusion problem of Equations (4 and 5) can be reduced to the following two equations^[36]

$$I_g = C_\mu \frac{du_h}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$I_g = -\frac{qL}{\tau_d} [A(u_g) - A(u_h)] \quad (7)$$

Here q is the elementary charge, u_h is the internal voltage in the channel. The ion transport time in the finite layer is

$$\tau_d = \frac{d^2}{D_{ion}} \quad (8)$$

The chemical capacitance is

$$C_\mu = -qL \frac{dA_{eq}}{du_g} \quad (9)$$

For the horizontal current, Figure 1c,d show the stationary (blue) and transient (green) source and drain current according to the direction of electrical field in the channel determined by the factor $\theta = V_{ds} / |V_{ds}|$ where V_{ds} is drain-source voltage. Changing the sign of θ allows to turn the response of the drain into the corresponding response of the source current, which can also be measured. The current is described by the equation^[27,36]

$$I_d = -\frac{q\theta L}{\tau_e} A - qL f_B \beta_\mu \frac{dA}{dt} \quad (10)$$

here

$$\tau_e = \frac{L^2}{\mu_p |V_{ds}|} \quad (11)$$

is the electronic transit time. The factor $0 < f_B < 1$ in Equation (10) appears in the process of integration of Equation (3). A transient

electronic current compensating the vertical ionic current is attributed to the source, and the remaining fraction f_B is attributed to the drain. Once the conservation equation (3) is split into two parts (for the drain and source current) providing Equation (10), $A(x)$ is treated as a homogeneous density along the channel. This derivation is explained in refs. [27,36], and different methods to determine f_B have been discussed in the literature.^[13,19,21,44] The factor

$$\beta_\mu = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{A}{\mu_p} \frac{d\mu_p}{dA}} \quad (12)$$

is due to the density dependence of the mobility.^[45] Note that it can be $\beta_\mu < 0$ if the mobility $d\mu_p/dA < 0$, which a common property.^[6,45,46]

In summary the model we use is composed of Equation (10), that is already obtained in the BM model,^[16] and Equation (7), which is a simplified coupled diffusion equation, that is further discussed in Sec. 2.5.^[27]

2.2. The Transient Response to Gate Voltage Step

Now we take an operating point V_g and we apply a small gate bias step perturbation $v_g = \Delta V H(t)$, where $H(t)$ is the unit step function. Based on Equations (6, 7, 10) we can obtain the shape of the resulting current transients. We summarize the procedures explained in ref. [27].

For a small perturbation, Equations (6, 7) can be expressed

$$\frac{dv_h}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\tau_d} (\Delta V + v_h) \quad (13)$$

Hence the time dependent voltage v_h inside the channel is

$$v_h = \Delta V (1 - e^{-t/\tau_d}) \quad (14)$$

We separate the drain current in Equation (10) in two components: the stationary

$$I_{d0}^{st} = -\frac{q\theta L}{\tau_e} A_{eq}(V_g) \quad (15)$$

and the time-dependent small perturbation component i_d

$$I_d(t) = I_{d0}^{st} + i_d(t) \quad (16)$$

For a small perturbation, Equation (10) gives the expression^[27]

$$i_d(t) = C_\mu \left[\frac{\theta}{\tau_e} v_h + f_B \beta_\mu \frac{dv_h}{dt} \right] \quad (17)$$

Using Equation (13)

$$i_d(t) = C_\mu \left[\frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} \Delta V + \left(\frac{\theta}{\beta_\mu \tau_e} - \frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} \right) v_h \right] \quad (18)$$

and we can write

$$i_d(t) = \left[\frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} + \left(\frac{\theta}{\beta_\mu \tau_e} - \frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} \right) (1 - e^{-t/\tau_d}) \right] C_\mu \Delta V \quad (19)$$

Figure 2. a) Scheme of the electrochemical transistor and the characteristic times processes. b) The stationary current according to the sign $\theta = V_{ds}/|V_{ds}|$ and c,d) the possible four different types of transient response with respect to time, for a step voltage at $V_g = -0.5$ V and $\Delta V = 0.1$ V at $t_0 = 0.50, 0.51$ ms. $A_0 = 6.2 \times 10^{12}$ m $^{-1}$, $V_v = 0$, $f_B = 0.5$, rest of parameters in Table 1.

To illustrate the transients in relation to a charging model, in **Figure 2** we consider a concrete expression of the thermodynamic function^[27]

$$A_{eq}(V_g) = \frac{2}{3} A_0 \left[\frac{q(V_v - V_g)}{k_B T} \right]^{3/2} \quad (20)$$

with the corresponding chemical capacitance

$$C_\mu = -qL \frac{dA_{eq}}{d(V_g)} = \frac{A_0}{k_B T} \left[\frac{q(V_v - V_g)}{k_B T} \right]^{1/2} \quad (21)$$

The k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, T the absolute temperature, V_v the valence edge potential, A_0 a density per length.

Figure 2 shows four current transient conditions, according to the sign of θ and the relative size of the dominant relaxation times τ_e and τ_d , by the parameters in **Table 1**. When $\theta = +1$, both jumps are larger than the final current. But if $\theta = -1$, one is larger and the other one smaller, so there is a point $\tau_e \approx \tau_d/f_B$ where the transient appears to vanish.

Table 1. Parameters of the transistor.

channel length	L	50 μ m
thickness	d	100 nm
width	w	10 μ m
Hole mobility	μ_p	0.02 cm 2 Vs $^{-1}$
Source-drain voltage	$ V_{ds} $	0.1 V
Thermal voltage	$k_B T/q$	0.026 V

The vertical diffusion resistance^[47] is

$$R_d = \frac{\tau_d}{C_\mu} \quad (22)$$

From Equation (19), the initial current value is

$$i_{d0} = \frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{R_d} \Delta V \quad (23)$$

The initial jump of the transient is a current through the vertical resistor R_d that starts charging the channel film and increasing the charge density. This is a typical initial jump of the current for a resistance in series with a capacitor, since the voltage in the capacitor is $v_\mu(t=0) = 0$, and in the first instant the applied voltage goes to the series resistance.

The time constants indicated in **Figure 2a** have different effects on the transients. The duration of the transient is set by τ_d , which is expressed in Equation (14). The initial jump is independent of τ_e . The final value of the step current is

$$i_{df} = C_\mu \frac{\theta}{\beta_\mu \tau_e} \Delta V \quad (24)$$

This value gives the post-jump equilibrium current, hence $I_{df}^{st} = I_{d0}^{st} + i_{df}$.

While the decay time is given by τ_d , the effect of τ_e occurs only when it is $\tau_e \geq \tau_d$. The quotient depends on several magnitudes in the relation

$$\frac{\tau_e}{\tau_d} = \left(\frac{L}{d} \right)^2 \frac{V_T}{|V_{ds}|} \frac{D_{ion}}{D_p} \quad (25)$$

where $V_T = k_B T/q$ is the thermal voltage, and D_p is the diffusion coefficient of holes.

Using the initial and final currents, the current transient in Equation (19) can be expressed as

$$i_d(t) = i_{df} \left[1 - \left(1 - \theta \frac{f_B \beta_\mu \tau_e}{\tau_d} \right) e^{-t/\tau_d} \right] \quad (26)$$

In the case $\beta_\mu = \theta = 1$ we have

$$i_d(t) = i_{df} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{f_B \tau_e}{\tau_d} \right) e^{-t/\tau_d} \right] \quad (27)$$

This is the standard expression of the transient in BM model,^[16,21,25,43] but BM use an ionic time τ_i instead of the diffusion time τ_d . We will explain this difference in Section 3.3.

The transients in **Figure 2** are highly characteristic, as shown in **Figure 3**.^[19] for a OECT made of the organic semiconductor poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) doped with poly(styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS). The PSS anions provide a counter charge for holes on the PEDOT chain and make the OECT channel conductive. A positive input voltage at the gate electrode modulates the channel current by pushing cations from the electrolyte into the PEDOT:PSS matrix. By changing the V_{ds} , one can modify τ_e , Equation (11). **Figure 3** presents the three possible cases of transients according to **Figure 2d**: **Figure 3a** is for $\tau_e > \tau_d$; **Figure 3c**

Figure 3. Experimental results of a–c) Change in the source current following a gate voltage step. The drain voltage is -30 mV for (a) -80 mV for (b) and -130 mV for (c). The gate voltage waveform is shown in the lower one-third of the panel in (a)–(c). The device had a channel width of $W = 260$ μm , a channel length of $L = 100$ μm , and a channel thickness of approximately $h = 150$ nm. Reproduced with permission from Friedlein, J.T., Donahue, M.J., Shaheen, S.E., Malliaras, G.G. and McLeod, R.R. (2016), Microsecond Response in Organic Electrochemical Transistors: Exceeding the Ionic Speed Limit. *Adv. Mater.*, 28: 8398–8404. © 2016 WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim.^[19]

is for $\tau_e < \tau_d$, and in Figure 3b it is $\tau_e \approx \tau_d/f_B$ and the transient appears to disappear according to Equation (27).

Note that the shapes of the small perturbation transients do not depend on the specific thermodynamic model of ion and electronic carriers in the channel. The chemical capacitance only gives the scale of the transient current, Equation (19). We can use any thermodynamic model that shows reasonable behavior (i.e., it must satisfy $C_\mu > 0$, avoiding phase transformations). For example, the model

$$A_{eq}(V_g) = \frac{C^*}{qL} (V_0 - V_g) \quad (28)$$

gives a constant chemical capacitance that is amply used^[10]

$$C_\mu = C^* \quad (29)$$

The shape of the transients will be the same as in the Figure 2.

The linearized equations that are found in BM and in the above diffusion model provide significant insight to the physical components of the transient. However, for a large step of V_g the linear model cannot be used, and it is necessary to solve the nonlinear system formed by Equations (6, 7, 10), or a more general simulation program, as in Sec. 5 of this paper. Due to nonlinear behavior, on and off switching times can be different,^[48] as observed experimentally in “asymmetric” switching times.^[34]

2.3. The Vertical Impedance

To represent the small signal equations in the frequency domain, we make $d/dt \rightarrow s = i\omega$, where ω is the angular frequency and $i = \sqrt{-1}$. We have

$$i_g = \frac{1}{R_d} (v_g - v_h) \quad (30)$$

$$i_g = C_\mu s v_h \quad (31)$$

Combining Equations (30) and (31) we obtain

$$i_g = \frac{1}{Z_d} v_g \quad (32)$$

where the diffusion impedance is

$$Z_d = R_d + \frac{1}{C_\mu s} \quad (33)$$

The vertical impedance in Equation (33) can be represented as an equivalent circuit shown in Figure 4a.^[36]

If we do not adopt the approximation (7), the vertical diffusion problem in a finite layer of Equations (4, 5) produces the transmission line model diffusion impedance given by^[47]

$$Z_{dl} = \frac{R_d}{(s/\omega_d)^{1/2}} \text{Cotanh} \left[(s/\omega_d)^{1/2} \right] \quad (34)$$

The model is shown in Figure 4d, and the impedance spectra are shown in Figure 4c. In Equation (34)

$$\omega_d = \frac{1}{\tau_d} \quad (35)$$

is the characteristic frequency of diffusion. It separates roughly the domain of spatially infinite diffusion, that displays a 45° line, and the low frequency behavior, that is a vertical line. The full transmission line model is shown in blue line, and the RC_μ approximation, where the series resistance is $R = R_d/3$, is shown in the vertical red line. It is indicated also the angular frequency

$$\omega_g = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \frac{1}{\tau_d} \quad (36)$$

Figure 4. a) The equivalent circuit for the vertical small signal ac impedance. b) The equivalent circuit for the transversal impedance. c) Complex plot impedance spectra. The blue line is the finite transmission line model in (d), and the red line is the $R_d C_\mu$ model in (a). The points indicate characteristic frequencies, $\omega_d = 1/\tau_d$, and the frequency of the turning point, $\omega_g = (\pi^2/2) \omega_d$. d) Transmission line diffusion impedance of a finite layer with blocking boundary condition.

that marks the turning point of the transition between the two regimes.^[47]

2.4. The Transversal Impedance

The horizontal current of Equation (10) can be written

$$I_d = -\frac{q\theta L}{\tau_e} A - \left(qL f_B \beta_\mu \frac{dA}{du_h} \right) \frac{du_h}{dt} \quad (37)$$

The prefactor of du_h/dt is a capacitance. Comparing with Equation (9) we can write

$$C_{tv} = f_B \beta_\mu C_\mu \quad (38)$$

and we obtain

$$I_d = -\frac{q\theta L}{\tau_e} A + C_{tv} \frac{du_h}{dt} \quad (39)$$

The “transversal capacitance” C_{tv} appearing in Equation (39) can be interpreted as the chemical capacitance of holes in the channel. It is the same as the chemical capacitance of ions C_μ due to electroneutrality, but the factors in Equation (38) (f_B, β_μ) indicate the part of the total chemical capacitance that contributes to the drain current.

From Equation (39) we find that the modulation of v_h induces a change of the drain current, according to the equation^[36]

$$i_d = \left(\frac{1}{R_{tv}} + C_{tv} s \right) v_h \quad (40)$$

where the transversal resistance

$$R_{tv} = \frac{\theta \beta_\mu \tau_e}{C_\mu} = \frac{\theta \beta_\mu L^2}{C_\mu \mu_p |u_{ds}|} \quad (41)$$

is associated to the modulation of the electronic carrier density by the gate voltage.

The effective relaxation time of the electronic channel, is

$$R_{tv} C_{tv} = \theta f_B \beta_\mu^2 \tau_e = \theta \tau_h \quad (42)$$

where

$$\tau_h = f_B \beta_\mu^2 \tau_e \quad (43)$$

The transverse impedance v_g/i_d is represented as an equivalent circuit in Figure 4b.^[36]

2.5. Evaluation of the RC Approximation to Diffusion

In the present and previous related works,^[27,36] we have converted Equations (2–5) into a simplified model formed by Equations (7, 10). We call the Equation (7) a simplified “diffusion” equation. By the transient solution of this system given in Equation (14), one can use the Equation (10), which is also a simplified solution of the horizontal transmission line problem in Equation (3), and one obtains the transients of i_d that we have described before in Figure 2. We remark that also the BM model consists essentially of an RC system, to which the horizontal transport Equation (10) is added.

To apply the mentioned approximations, certain conditions must be satisfied in the way that the ionic-electronic charge is distributed in the channel film. We can describe the situation with reference to Figure 1b. When the dopant ions are inserted, they must produce a nearly homogeneous vertical distribution. Otherwise, the hole horizontal current depends on height y , and Equations (4 and 5) become two coupled transmission lines that can only be solved by the usual simulation programs.^[19,38,41–43] If, on the other hand, Equation (7) is accepted, then it can be combined with the BM-type approximation of Equation (3), namely, Equation (10), and valuable solutions are obtained.

The question is, when are these solutions reliable and valuable for describing experimental results?

Intuitively we can see that if the measurement time is much shorter than τ_d , the charge distribution will be inhomogeneous, as the perturbation injected at the boundary with the electrolyte does not yet extend deeply to the channel height. When $t > \tau_d$ it is likely that a homogeneous distribution is achieved, and the above approximations are valid.

To evaluate this picture quantitatively we need to solve the diffusion problem formed by Equations (4, 5), when a step concentration $a(0, t) = a_0$ is applied to a layer where initially a

Figure 5. The charging of a layer of thickness d by application of a step of concentration a_0 at the left boundary. The blue line is the full solution, the red line is the exponential approximation, and the brown line is the Erfc approximation. a) Carrier distribution into the layer at different times. b) The concentration at $y = d/2$ as a function of time.

= 0 and $J_v(y = d) = 0$ at all times. The solution is given in Ref. [47]:

$$\frac{a(y, t)}{a_0} = 1 - 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \beta_m^{-1} \sin\left(\beta_m \frac{y}{d}\right) \exp\left(-\beta_m^2 \frac{D_n t}{d^2}\right) \quad (44)$$

where $\beta_m = \pi(m - \frac{1}{2})$ with $m = 1, 2, \dots$

There are two important limit cases. At late times $t > \tau_d$, only the $m = 1$ term in the above sum contributes substantially, and $a(x, t)$ is well approximated by

$$\frac{a(y, t)}{a_0} = 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{2d}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{t}{T_d}\right) \quad (45)$$

here

$$T_d = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \tau_d \quad (46)$$

Conversely, at early times, diffusion is hardly affected by the blocking boundary at $x = L$, and we may solve Equation (5) in a semi-infinite geometry $y \in [0, \infty)$ instead, yielding

$$\frac{a(y, t)}{a_0} = \text{Erfc}\left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{4D_{ion}t}}\right) \quad (47)$$

in terms of the error function.

In Figure 5a is represented the solution of charging the layer at different times (blue). At very short time the exponential approximation (red) is far from accurate, while the Erfc approximation describes the transient well. But at $t = 0.2 \tau_d$ and longer time the exponential solution is quite accurate. In Figure 5b is shown the

concentration at the midpoint of the layer as a function of time. Again at $t = 0.2 \tau_d$ and longer times the red exponential approximation is quite good.

In Figure 6 is shown the drain current obtained applying the Equation (10) to the concentration at midpoint as a function of time, for the two cases of Figure 2d. Since an average charge is used as A in Equation (10), we can see that in the very first instants this approximation cannot be applied, due to strong ions inhomogeneity in the vertical direction. But for $t = 0.2 \tau_d$ and longer times the approximation of the exponential decay provides a good description of the excess transient current (for $\tau_e > \tau_d$, Figure 6a,b) or the defect current (for $\tau_e < \tau_d$, Figure 6c,d). In the first instants there is an excess or defect peak over the exponential line, that is due to the initial Erfc response.

Based on this analysis we obtain better insight to the significance of the approximations. With respect to the impedance response in Figure 4c, the initial brown line of the decay in Figure 6 corresponds to the 45° Warburg line. And the exponential red line of the transient corresponds to the vertical RC line in Figure 4c. By comparing the frequency of the turning point, $f_g = \omega_g / 2\pi$, and the decay time T_d in Equation (46), we can see that they are related by

$$f_g = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{1}{T_d} \quad (48)$$

We now state the validity of the developments based on the simplified diffusion equation (7), or the utilization of the $R_d C_\mu$ circuit instead of the transmission line. This approximation cannot describe the impedance spectra or the current transients at frequencies higher or times shorter than indicated in Equation (48). Such “fast” domains cannot be treated by the methods described in this paper; they must be treated separately. But at the longer times, the simplified analysis is quite useful. In the measurement, a small overshoot will appear in the log representation as shown in Figure 6b. This is the initial diffusion domain. Thereafter, the exponential approximation is quite good, and enables to combine the diffusion charging with other aspects of the system, as we discuss in the Section 3 of this paper.

2.6. Depletion Mode Transistor

This is the case $A = 0$, cation density $Z = M$, and hole carrier density $P = P_0 - M$, where P_0 is the initial doping. The model equations are^[27]

$$I_h(L) = -\theta \frac{qL}{\tau_e} (P_0 - M) + qfL \frac{dM}{dt} \quad (49)$$

$$\tau_d \frac{dM}{dt} = M_{eq} (u_g) - M \quad (50)$$

In the small perturbation we obtain

$$I_d = -\theta \frac{qL}{\tau_e} (P_0 - M(u_{g0})) + C_\mu \left(\frac{\theta}{\tau_e} v_h + f_B \frac{dv_h}{dt} \right) \quad (51)$$

Comparing with Equation (17), we remark that the stationary expressions are different in accumulation and depletion, but the

Figure 6. Evolution of the drain current during the charging of the channel, calculated by Equation (10) taking the concentration at $y = d/2$. The blue line is the full solution, the red line is the exponential approximation, and the brown line is the Erfc approximation. (a) and (c) are for different ratios of the characteristic times, the panels below show the same transient in Log vertical axis.

small perturbation method can be applied equally to both. Hence the forthcoming extensions apply equally to both types.

3. Model of Transients with Diffusion and Interfacial/Electrolyte Impedances

3.1. The Vertical Current/Voltage Equations

To represent the electrolyte and interfacial limitations we add to the model of Figure 4a the parallel combination of ionic resistance R_i and double layer capacitance C_d as shown in Figure 7a.^[49,50] We aim to find a solution of the transient voltage and current for the extended system. The new vertical circuit is represented in the equivalent circuit of Figure 7b. We remark that in an OCET model the C_d must be combined with a *parallel* resistance, since the ionic current must penetrate the channel, and cannot be blocked at the interface.

Figure 7. a) Scheme of the measurement of transient response of the OEET with series resistance and capacitor in the electrolyte. b) The equivalent circuit for the vertical small signal ac impedance. c) The equivalent circuit for the transversal impedance.

The vertical current provides three equations^[27]

$$I_g = \frac{1}{R_i} (u_g - u_s) + C_d \frac{d(u_g - u_s)}{dt} \quad (52)$$

$$I_g = -\frac{qL}{\tau_d} [A(u_s) - A(u_h)] \quad (53)$$

$$I_g = C_\mu \frac{du_h}{dt} \quad (54)$$

Here u_s is the voltage at the outer surface of the channel.

3.2. The Transient of the Vertical Current

To obtain the time-dependent currents in Figure 7a, we apply the same small perturbation method as in Sec. 2. We solve the response to an applied signal in the frequency domain. The solution in the time domain will be then obtained by inverse Laplace transform.

The vertical current equations become

$$i_g = \left(\frac{1}{R_i} + C_d s \right) (v_g - v_s) \quad (55)$$

$$i_g = \frac{1}{R_d} (v_s - v_h) \quad (56)$$

$$i_g = C_\mu s v_h \quad (57)$$

We define the relaxation times

$$\tau_s = R_i C_d \quad (58)$$

$$\tau_{R\mu} = R_i C_\mu \quad (59)$$

and by Equation (20)

$$\tau_d = R_d C_\mu \quad (60)$$

The above equations yield the relation

$$v_h = \frac{1 + \tau_s s}{(1 + \tau_s s)(1 + \tau_d s) + \tau_{R\mu} s} v_g \quad (61)$$

Equation (61) is the response of the internal voltage in the channel to the gate voltage perturbation.

Solving the quadratic equation in the denominator, and noting that $v_g = \Delta V/s$, we can write

$$v_h = \frac{1 + \tau_s s}{s(1 - \tau_1 s)(1 + \tau_2 s)} \Delta V \quad (62)$$

The fundamental relaxation times are

$$\tau_1 = 2 \frac{\tau_0}{1 - b} \quad (63)$$

$$\tau_2 = 2 \frac{\tau_0}{1 + b} \quad (64)$$

where

$$\tau_0 = \left[\frac{1}{\tau_d} \left(1 + \frac{C_\mu}{C_d} \right) + \frac{1}{\tau_s} \right]^{-1} \quad (65)$$

$$b = \left(1 - 4 \frac{\tau_0^2}{\tau_d \tau_s} \right)^{1/2} \quad (66)$$

By inversion of (62) to the time domain we have the solution

$$v_h = [1 - (\delta_1 e^{-t/\tau_1} + \delta_2 e^{-t/\tau_2})] \Delta V \quad (67)$$

$$\delta_1 = \frac{\tau_0}{b \tau_d} \left(\frac{\tau_1}{\tau_s} - 1 \right) \quad (68)$$

$$\delta_2 = \frac{\tau_0}{b \tau_d} \left(1 - \frac{\tau_2}{\tau_s} \right) \quad (69)$$

Equation (67) is the relaxation of the internal voltage when a pulse $v_g = \Delta V$ is applied to the gate contact. This result extends Equation (13)14 to the more general situation. Note that $v_h(0) = 0$, $v_h(\infty) = \Delta V$. The $v_h(t)$ is not dependent on τ_e since there is no horizontal component of the perturbation. However, this simplification will change if τ_e is very long and influences the diffusion transport.^[27]

For the interpretation of these results, we turn to **Figure 8**. The two fundamental decay time constants, τ_1 and τ_2 are plotted with respect to C_d/C_μ in **Figure 8a**, and the weights in the voltage transient δ_i are shown in **Figure 8b**. Note that $\tau_2 \approx \tau_0$ at all values of C_d . The voltage transient is shown in **Figure 8d**, indicating the contribution of each component, for a particular value of C_d (the dot in **Figure 8a**).

The times τ_1 and τ_2 become independent of C_d at low and high C_d , respectively. To obtain the limiting values we first find the limits of τ_0 . For $C_d \ll C_\mu$ it is

$$\tau_{0L} = \left[\frac{1}{C_d R_d} + \frac{1}{\tau_s} \right]^{-1} = \left[\frac{1}{R_d} + \frac{1}{R_i} \right]^{-1} C_d \quad (70)$$

This is the charging of the surface capacitor C_d . While for $C_d \gg C_\mu$

$$\tau_{0H} = \left[\frac{1}{\tau_d} + \frac{1}{\tau_s} \right]^{-1} \quad (71)$$

Here is the charging of the surface capacitor limited by the charging of the chemical capacitance when C_d becomes large.

In **Figure 8b** we note that for $C_d \ll C_\mu$ the decay is dominated by τ_1 , and it can be approximated as

$$\tau_{1L} = (R_i + R_d) C_\mu \quad (72)$$

For $C_d \gg C_\mu$, it is $\delta_1 \approx 0$ and $\delta_2 \approx 1$. Hence the second root dominates the decay for $C_d \gg C_\mu$, and it becomes

$$\tau_{2H} = \tau_{0H} = R_d C_\mu = \tau_d \quad (73)$$

Accordingly, we find that τ_2 corresponds to the original time constant τ_d in the diffusion model of **Figures 1 and 2**, while τ_1 contains a contribution of the series resistance, Equation (72), and it is always

$$\tau_{2H} < \tau_{1L} \quad (74)$$

and, more generally

$$\tau_2 < \tau_1 \quad (75)$$

Therefore, there are two components in the transient of v_h toward ΔV . τ_2 is the fast component and τ_1 the slow one, **Figure 8d**. The diffusion charging (τ_2) happens first, and then occurs a slower charging due to the external resistor and capacitor (τ_1).

3.3. The Transient of the Horizontal Current

We can write Equation (40) as

$$i_d = \frac{1}{R_{iv}} (1 + \theta \tau_h s) v_h \quad (76)$$

Therefore

$$i_d = \frac{\theta}{R_{iv}} \frac{(1 + \tau_s s)(1 + \theta \tau_h s)}{(1 + \tau_1 s)(1 + \tau_2 s)} \frac{\Delta V}{s} \quad (77)$$

This model corresponds to **Figure 7c**.^[36] The solution in the time domain is

$$i_d(t) = \left[\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} \right) + \alpha_2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}} \right) \right] \frac{\theta C_\mu}{\beta_\mu \tau_e} \Delta V \quad (78)$$

Figure 8. Model simulations of the system of Figure 7. a) The relaxation times. The point indicates the value used in (d,e). b,c) The weight factors of the transients. Parameters: $\tau_d = 0.1$ ms, $\tau_e = 0.5$ ms, $f_B = 0.5$, $R_i = 0.2$ Ω , $C_\mu = 2$ mF. d,e) The transients of ν_h and i_d for $C_d = 1$ mF. The grey dashed line is the final equilibrium.

where

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{\theta \tau_s \tau_h}{\tau_1 \tau_2} \quad (79)$$

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{(\tau_2 - \tau_1)} \left(-\tau_1 + \theta \tau_h + \tau_s - \frac{\theta \tau_h \tau_s}{\tau_1} \right) \quad (80)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{1}{(\tau_2 - \tau_1)} \left(\tau_2 - \theta \tau_h - \tau_s + \frac{\theta \tau_h \tau_s}{\tau_2} \right) \quad (81)$$

We observe in Equation (78) that the current transient contains two components governed by the fundamental time constants, τ_1 and τ_2 . The weights of the components are shown in Figure 8c. The initial value of the current response is

$$i_{d,in} = \alpha_0 \frac{\Delta V}{R_{tv}} \quad (82)$$

and the final value is

$$i_{d,fin} = \frac{\Delta V}{R_{tv}} \quad (83)$$

As commented before, τ_2 is the fast component, and this is observed in Figure 8e, where the initial spike is the same as that in Figure 2d, since $\tau_d < \tau_h$ in this example. But then the signal rises to a larger final value, due to the longer time constant τ_1 .

In Figure 9 we show results for the opposite case in Figure 2, $\tau_d > \tau_h$. In Figure 9d we remark the rise of the voltage by the combination of the two fundamental time constants. In Figure 9e we observe the components of the rise of the current: It starts at $\alpha_0 \approx 0.2$, shows a rapid rise by τ_2 , and a longer rise by τ_1 .

By Equation (72) we can observe that

$$\tau_{1L} = R_i C_\mu \quad (84)$$

Figure 9. Model simulations of the system of Figure 7. a) The relaxation times. The point indicates the value used in (d,e). b,c) The weight factors of the transients. Parameters: $\tau_d = 0.3$ ms, $\tau_e = 0.1$ ms, $f_B = 0.5$, $R_i = 0.4$ Ω , $C_\mu = 2$ mF. d,e) The transients of v_h and i_d for $C_d = 2$ mF. The grey dashed line is the final equilibrium.

in the case in which the outer resistance is dominant. This is the time called τ_i in the Bernards-Malliaras model, where the transient is usually written as Equation (27), with τ_i instead of the diffusion time τ_d . Note that BM model obtains a RC circuit similar to Figure 4a but the resistance is interpreted as electrolyte transport.^[16,18] Instead, in Figure 4a R_d and C_μ are associated to ion diffusion and accumulation inside the channel.^[36]

We arrive at the conclusion that BM expression is a particular case of Equation (78), that contains both the external ionic resistance and diffusion inside the channel, represented by a “volume capacitance.”

Again, we remark that for a large voltage step the full set of nonlinear equations must be solved to obtain the transient response.

4. Interpretation of the Transients

Based on the insights obtained in the preceding sections we provide more detailed interpretation for analysis of the transients of OECT and the identification of their components in experimental results.

As we commented in Figure 1a the basic measurement consists of application of a step of the gate voltage and the measurement of the drain current. Consider in Figure 10 a system in the absence of series elements, that was already solved in Figure 2. There are two components to the transient. One is the exponential evolution of the internal voltage v_h , indicated in Equation (14) and shown in Figure 10a. This is associated fully to the vertical impedance. Next, the change of v_h produces a change of i_d , given

Figure 10. The transients in a system with diffusion charging, without series elements ($R_i = 0 \Omega$). a) Voltage in the film, b) drain current. Purple: $\tau_d = 0.2 \text{ ms}$, $R_d = 0.1 \Omega$, green: $\tau_d = 0.08 \text{ ms}$, $R_d = 0.04 \Omega$. Parameters: $\tau_e = 1.2 \text{ ms}$, $f_B = 0.5$, $C_\mu = 2 \text{ mF}$. c) The equivalent circuit part that controls each transient. The transient of the voltage is determined by the vertical impedance (red). The transient of the drain current incorporates the horizontal channel impedance (green), to form the final transverse impedance.

in Equation (24), and the corresponding examples in Figure 2b, shown also in Figure 10b.

The exponential form in Equation (14) arises from the $R_d C_\mu$ approximation that comes from Equation (7). This is not accurate at times shorter than τ_d , as we have discussed in Figures 5 and 6. The $R_d C_\mu$ approximation cannot capture the initial diffusion part that corresponds to the 45° line in the impedance of Figure 4c. Therefore, it is highly recommended to combine the analysis of transients with the measurement of impedance spectroscopy, that reveals the semi-infinite diffusion domain. Another important reason is that the $R_d C_\mu$ approximation cannot distinguish a possible series resistance R_i from the true diffusion resistance R_d , as they are connected in series. This is indicated in Figure 10c. The impedance spectra can produce such distinction, as a series resistance simply displaces the transmission line spectra.

Now we highlight the essential role of the chemical capacitance in the transient dynamics. By using the $R_d C_\mu$ approximation in Figure 10c we observe that the chemical capacitance is the element that controls the conductivity of the channel and governs the interesting properties such as synapsis potentiation, as the charge in C_μ keeps the memory of previous stimuli. Here the $R_d C_\mu$ approximation provides a strong insight into the transistor operation, that is obscured if we keep the whole transmission line in the vertical impedance.

In both systems of Figure 10a the chemical capacitance is the same. In the green system the ion diffusion coefficient is larger, the diffusion resistance is smaller, and thus the τ_d is smaller, than in the purple system. This difference translates into the different spikes of Figure 10b, and the different forms of Figure 2, according to the relation (25) between τ_d and τ_e .

As we have already mentioned, the chemical capacitance is a necessary part of the system, which gives the changes of carrier number in response to the change of gate voltage. But there are other possible capacitances in the system, as shown in Figure 7. In Sec. 3 we have developed a long analysis to clarify their consequences in the dynamic response. We now present some additional cases of the system of Figure 7 for discussion.

In Figure 11 we compare two systems with the same chemical capacitance C_μ . In the blue system $C_d = 0.8 \text{ mF}$, and we see in Figure 11b that the voltage transient is mainly controlled by τ_1 , while in the purple system $C_d = 30 \text{ mF}$ and the transient is governed by τ_2 . Hence the voltage transient of the purple system is faster in Figure 11c.

Another important feature is the different signatures of the drain current to approach equilibrium, either by direct decay, as in Figure 2, or by an initial spike followed by a rise of current, that did not occur in Figure 2. We find this composed pattern in Figure 8e and in the blue line in Figure 11e. This behavior is relevant for synapsis operation. In two-contact devices we can distinguish two main patterns: current decay, in capacitive systems, and a rise of current, in inductive systems, that are associated with synapse depression and potentiation, respectively.^[48,51]

As shown in Figure 2d in the transistor system the rise or decay behavior is due to the relation between τ_d and τ_h . We note in Equations (80 and 81) that α_1 , that determines the long-time decay of i_d , depends on the difference of τ_1 and τ_h , while α_2 , that governs the short-time decay, depends on the difference of τ_2 and τ_h . In the magenta case of Figure 11, $\tau_1 < \tau_h$. Since α_1 is mostly negative, the decay of the current is “capacitive” and decreases monotonously. In the blue case $\tau_1 > \tau_h$, with $\alpha_1 > 0$, and the long-time current increases in “inductive” case. Thus τ_1 in Figure 11 plays the role of τ_d in Figure 2d. But now τ_1 is mainly due to the external RC elements, not the diffusion charging. In addition, τ_2 contains the fastest component of the decay, mainly determine by the diffusion insertion of ions. To confirm this interpretation, we show in Figure 12 two more cases where the diffusion time τ_d is fully negligible with the respect to the ionic charging time (hence no dashed line is seen in Figure 12b). Again, we can obtain in Figure 12c the two cases of Figure 2d, raising or decaying.

5. Visualizing the Interface Phenomena through 2D Device Modelling

The solubility difference is the most notable chemical-physics mechanism that defines the discontinuity associated with the interface between the solution and the semiconductor. This section aims to show how this would lead to an effective circuit of resistance in parallel to capacitance and that the resulting effect on the current transient agrees with the analytical model. We use the same simulation approach reported in refs. [24,27], which consists of employing the Sentaurus device TCAD by Synopsys to solve ionic and electronic transport within a semiconductor device model framework. To our previous reports,^[24,27] we need to add the potential solubility difference at the solution/semiconductor interface with the ions being less soluble in the semiconductor. Henry’s law for solubility^[52] can be used to show that solubility difference dictates a concentration ratio between the two sides of the interface. Such a concentration

Figure 11. Comparison of transients for the system of Figure 7. Common parameters: Parameters: $\tau_d = 0.2$ ms, $\tau_e = 1.2$ ms, $f_B = 0.5$, $C_\mu = 2$ mF, $R_d = 0.1$ Ω . Purple: $R_i = 0.1$ Ω , $C_d = 30$ mF, blue: $R_i = 0.5$ Ω , $C_d = 0.8$ mF. a) Shows the relaxation times as function of C_d/C_μ . The points in the x-axis indicate the values of C_d . b) The weights of the voltage decay. c) The evolution of v_h . The dashed lines show the decay of $\delta_2 e^{-t/\tau_2}$. d) The amplitudes of the decay of i_d as function of C_d/C_μ . e) The evolution of i_d .

(density) ratio corresponds to an energy barrier within a semiconductor device model framework. Hence, we will implement an energy barrier (E_b) that will enforce a density ratio of $\exp(-E_b/k_B T)$.

Figure 13a shows the OECT device structure used in the simulations, and Table 2 lists the parameters implemented in the simulations. It is a P type OECT based on an undoped semiconductor where the penetration of anions from the solution would dope and switch it on. We show the hole density distribution inside the semiconductor for $V_{DS} = -0.1$ V, $V_{GS} = -0.05$ V, and $I_{DS} = 10$ μ A (see red circle in Figure 13b). The source/drain overlap is 5 μ m, making the double layer capacitance insignificant for the device operation. The solution concentration, ion diffusivity, and

distance of the gate electrode (Table 2 and Figure 13a) ensured the solution serial resistance was negligible.

In these simulations, the cations are insoluble in the semiconductor, and the anions injection barrier at the solution/semiconductor interface was implemented by enforcing a ratio of $\exp(-E_b/k_B T)$ between the anions on the semiconductor and solution sides of the interface. We first simulated the output characteristics of OECTs with different ionic injection barriers. Figure 13b shows the output IV curves of OECTs having ionic injection barrier (E_b) of 0 eV (red line), 0.1 eV (orange line), 0.2 eV (green line), and 0.3 eV (cyan line). As expected, an injection barrier shifts the curve by the amount equivalent to the barrier energy converted to volts. (denoted $V_T = E_b/q$).

Figure 12. Comparison of transients for the system of Figure 7. Common parameters: Parameters: $\tau_d = 0.01$ ms, $\tau_e = 1.2$ ms, $f_B = 0.5$, $C_\mu = 2$ mF, $R_d = 0.005$ Ω . Orange: $R_i = 0.1$ Ω , $C_d = 0.02$ mF, purple: $R_i = 0.5$ Ω , $C_d = 0.02$ mF. a) Shows the relaxation times. The points in the x-axis indicate the values of C_d . b) The weights of the voltage decay. c) The evolution of ν_h . d) The amplitudes α_1 of the decay of i_d as function of C_d/C_μ . ($\alpha_2 \approx \alpha_0 \approx -60$.) e) The evolution of i_d .

To understand the effect of the anions injection barrier on the interface properties, we plot in **Figure 14** the charge carriers' density distribution close to the interface (black line) between the semiconductor (left) and the solution (right). The charge carriers are anions (red line), cations (cyan line), and holes (green line). To place the devices with different injection barriers on equal footings, we chose gate voltages such that $(V_{GS} + V_T)$ is equal for the devices ($=50$ mV). Indeed, the hole and anion density in the bulk of the devices are identical (1.5×10^{19} cm $^{-3}$). The inherent discontinuity at the solution/semiconductor interface is expected to induce some polarization. **Figure 14a** shows that without an ionic injection barrier, it extends about 1 nm from the interface. Considering **Figure 14**, an ionic barrier produces a lower anion density on the semiconductor side, resulting in a higher injection resistance. Also, the ionic barrier induces hole

and anion accumulation at the interface, possibly considered a double-layer capacitance. Between $E_b = 0.2$ eV and $E_b = 0.3$ eV, the anion density at the interface is reduced by 30, and the integrated net charge close to the interface goes up by a factor of 1.7.

To simulate the transient response of the different devices, we applied a step to the gate bias, ensuring that the ON state corresponds to the same bias used for **Figure 14** ($V_{GS} + V_T = 50$ mV). A barrier of 0.1 eV had a negligible effect, and **Figure 15** shows the responses for ionic injection barrier (E_b) of 0 eV (red line), 0.2 eV (green line), and 0.3 eV (cyan line). The longer time constant associated with a higher barrier aligns with our observation (**Figure 13**) that the barrier induces a capacitance and a resistance. Based on our analysis of **Figure 14**, the interface resistance is the dominant factor.

Figure 13. a) Schematic description of the OECT device structure exhibiting the hole density distribution for $V_{GS} = 0$ V, $V_{DS} = -0.1$ V, and no ionic injection barrier at the solution/semiconductor interface. b) Current gate-voltage (output characteristics) of OECT devices for different ion injection barriers between the solution and the semiconductor. The lines show no-barrier (red line), 0.1 (orange line), 0.2 (green line), and 0.3 eV (cyan line). The red circle shows the point at which the densities in (a) were simulated. Note that the ion injection barrier shifts the curves (as a V_T shift).

Table 2. Device and material parameters used in the simulations.

Device	Channel length	50 μm
	Channel width	50 μm
Semiconductor	Thickness	100 nm
	Hole mobility	5 $\text{cm}^2 \text{Vs}^{-1}$
	Source-drain voltage	0.1 V
	Anion diffusivity	$10^{-8} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
Solution	Cation diffusivity	–
	Anion diffusivity	$10^{-6} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
	Cation diffusivity	$10^{-6} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
	Salt concentration	10^{20}cm^{-3} (0.17 M)

6. Conclusion

We established a general theory of the current transient of ionic-electronic transistors. The dominant effect when the gate voltage

is changed is a transient charging of the channel by diffusion of ions. The additional influence of electrolyte capacitance and resistance splits the fundamental time constant of diffusion τ_d into two different components, τ_1 and τ_2 . There are different possible origins to the widely observed transient currents in OECTs. The diffusion charging must be there, as this is the fundamental physical component: the charging of the chemical capacitance. The current transient, however, may be dominated either by the diffusion elements or by external elements. The transient may become much larger than by diffusion alone by impediments of ion transport.

In the BM model, external elements have the leading role. We have provided a more complete classification of the physical factors governing the transient response. The main property determining the shape of the transient is the signs of α_1 and α_2 , which produces capacitive-like decay in the negative case, and inductive-like current rise in the positive cases. The modulation of response shapes according to the intrinsic parameters provides an essential control of synaptic properties as such

Figure 14. Simulated charge carriers' density distribution close to the interface (black line) between the semiconductor (left) and the solution (right). The densities are along a cutline in the middle between the source and drain electrodes. The charge carriers are anions (red line), cations (cyan line), and holes (green line). No ionic injection barrier a) ($E_b = 0$), b) $E_b = 0.2$ eV, and c) $E_b = 0.3$ eV. The circled + and – denote the net charge at the interface.

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Figure 15. Transient responses of the devices having different injection barriers following a gate voltage step from 0.2 V to the voltage corresponding to $I_D = 10 \mu\text{A}$ (i.e., to the same $V_G - V_T$). $V_{DS} = -0.1\text{V}$. The inset is a zoom on the first 20 ms.

as STD, STP and LTP in neuromorphic applications. In practice, a combination of experimental techniques is necessary to discriminate the physical origin of the observed transients. The analysis of simulations enables to include more complete effects as the distribution of oppositely charged ions, but confirms the general trends obtained in the theory model. This method provides a convenient framework for the characterization of complex time domains responses of organic electrochemical transistors.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340763>, reference number 3340763.

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